

PROBING THE COLD GAS CONTENT OF NORMAL STAR-FORMING GALAXIES AT $3 < Z < 3.5$ WITH ALMA

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History of star-formation

20x increase in the first 3 Gyr

number of stars born /volume /time

what drives such fast increase?

THE MISSING PIECE: PROBING THE COLD GAS

Image credit: MPIA / G. Sunson / A. V. Macciò

cold gas fuels both
star-formation and
BH accretion

I. Dust continuum as a tracer of molecular gas

ALMA Cycle 2
Band 6 ~240GHz
~300 μm rest-frame

- ALMA detected
- ALMA undetected
- ALMA detected AGN
- ALMA undetected AGN

SFR with magphys, including ALMA: 0.5 dex higher than optical-NIR sed fitting

COSMOS-ACS field
zspec from
VUDS&zCOSMOS

Molecular gas content of 45 MS star-forming galaxies at $z \sim 3.2$

Schinnerer+16

$$t_{\text{depl}} = M_{\text{gas}} / \text{SFR}$$

USE CO LINES

Target selection
5 highest S/N dust
continuum from
Schinnerer+16

ALMA observations

- Cycle 3-4, PI: Cassata
- 4.4h total, **2.2h on target**
- band 3 & band 4
- CO(5-4) & CO(4-3)
[CO(3-2) for one]
- 0.6'' resolution

band 6: gas mass
 $10^{11}-10^{11.2} M_{\odot}$
band 4: within $\pm 20\%$ band 6

$T_{\text{depl}} 0.3-2 \text{ Gyr}$

$M_{\text{gas}}/M_{\text{tot}} 65-85\%$

new!! band 4: 135 GHz observed \sim 500 μ m rest-frame

$$FWHM_{CO(5-4)} = 196 \pm 12$$

$$FWHM_{CO(4-3)} = 242 \pm 24$$

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Gal 2 [$\sim 1.2 \times MS$]

$$FWHM_{CO(5-4)} = 321 \pm 23$$

$$FWHM_{CO(4-3)} = 498 \pm 70$$

HST F814W

UVISTA K_s

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HST F814W

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Gal 3 [$\sim 1.25 \times M_S$]

$FWHM_{CO(5-4)} = 563 \pm 46$
 $FWHM_{CO(4-3)} = 368 \pm 85$

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Gal 4 [3.2xMS]

$\text{FWHM}_{\text{CO}(5-4)} = 555 \pm 23$
 $\text{FWHM}_{\text{CO}(4-3)} = 365 \pm 22$

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Gal 5 [$\sim 1.4 \times MS$]

gal5_line_co_band3.image93-112.pbcor.image-ras

gal5_cont_band4.image.pbcor.image-raster

$$FWHM_{CO(5-4)} = 377 \pm 24$$

$$FWHM_{CO(4-3)} = 314 \pm 47$$

gal5_line_co_band4.image_42-85.pbcor.image-raster

Gal 5 [$\sim 1.4 \times \text{MS}$]

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- **CO(5-4)** detected at **$>5\sigma$** for all 5 galaxies
- **CO(4-3)** (or **CO(3-2)**) detected at **$>3\sigma$** for 4 galaxies (**2σ** for one)
- 500 μ m rest-frame continuum detected at **$>3\sigma$** for all 5 galaxies
- (marginally) **spatially extended**
- FWHM(lines) \sim **200-600 km/s**, with tails up to 1000 km/s
- **Large spatial offsets** between ALMA and optical/NIR
- Offsets also between CO transitions: **probing different phases?**
- **Pair/merger/compact** morphology

Compilation of high-z galaxies with CO detections

zooming in...

the largest sample of MS galaxies with CO detections at $z > 3$

the largest sample of MS galaxies with multiple CO detections at $z > 2$

fair correlation with L_{FIR}
 extended by an order of magnitude!

CO SLED: Spectral Line Energy Distribution for CO lines

1. Obtain CO(1-0)

2. Constrain excitation source

Do they make sense?

typical slope of more energetic objects, like QSO, starbursts

typical slopes of SMG/BzKs

Carilli & Walter + 13, ARAA

Summarizing:

gal 1 & 2: ~BzK

gal 3, 4 & 5: QSO/Starburst

$$M_{\text{gas}} = L'_{\text{CO}(1-0)} * \alpha_{\text{CO}}$$

Carilli & Walter + 13, ARAA

$$\alpha_{\text{CO}} = 3.7 \text{ [Tacconi + 17 recipe]}$$

CO vs dust as M_{gas} estimators

CO: gas mass
 $10^{10.7} - 10^{11.3} M_{\odot}$

slightly broader than
continuum

$T_{\text{depl}} 0.15 - 1.8 \text{ Gyr}$

$M_{\text{gas}}/M_{\text{tot}} 45 - 85\%$

$t_{\text{depl}} = M_{\text{gas}} / \text{SFR}$ vs z

gas fractions vs z

compilation by Dessauges-Zavadsky+16

$$t_{\text{depl}} = M_{\text{gas}} / \text{SFR} \text{ vs } z$$

$$\mu_{\text{gas}} \text{ VS } Z$$

Schinnerer+16

CONCLUSIONS?

- gas masses from **dust continuum vs CO** in decent **agreement**
- **Diversity** of CO **SLEDs**:
 - 2 galaxies seem **normal MS galaxies**; medium-long gas depletion timescale, large gas reservoir
 - 3 other galaxies powered by a more energetic source; possibly obscured **QSO? Mergers/Starbursts** on the MS? See Elbaz talk
- **Offsets** between ALMA and optical/NIR, and also between two CO transitions, and between CO and continuum: multiple components? See Puglisi talk

- A lot of information: **just started digging**

- modelling of spectra, dynamical masses

- revise SEDs

- “aperture” CO photometry

Wish list

- HST/WFC3** and **SINFONI** will reveal dynamical state; **JVLA** will reveal true CO(1-0) (deadline august 2017)
- Submitted cycle 5 proposal to get **high-resolution ALMA** imaging of CO(5-4)
- Submitted cycle 4 proposal to get **CO(7-6) and C(2-1)** (PI: Daizhong Liu)

